

SensApp

D5.1 Report on sensitivity and specificity for A β 1-42

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Author(s)	Martina Mugnano
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1. Introduction

The reaction steps after spotting the glass slides by DSS have been performed fully manually in CNR labs, due to the lack of liquid handling automation from Ginolis. This led CNR to spend additional efforts and time for implementing the manual steps and for achieving a reasonable standardization, especially crucial when working with the challenging samples at low abundant proteins. In fact, even little variations in handling the reagents and the slides produce variations in background levels and non-specific signals that can be highly detrimental, especially at low concentrations. Therefore, the experimental activities for characterizing the limit of detection and for building the calibration lines in pure protein samples took longer than expected and only the last two months of the project (M41 and M42) were focused on the experiments with body fluids.

The functionalized slides undergo degradation of the reactive surface through contact with air and humidity, and therefore they must be used as soon as possible after opening the package. Also in this case, this is particularly detrimental when working with challenging samples at high dilutions. In fact, the lack of automated reaction steps prevented us from using more than 2 slides per day, thus facing the additional issue of reactivity degradation over days. Concerning the experiments in body fluids, we followed the suggestions from the reviewers in the second-year review meeting by focusing the attention on body fluids lower in proteins than plasma, such as urine and saliva, also considering the limited time available. In addition, the results obtained with fluids alternative to plasma and serum can launch the DSS technology towards applications on other kinds of biomarker targets.

The dissemination level of this Deliverable D5.1 is public. We achieved various results in this workpackage which are currently under consideration for exploitation in patents and scientific publications. Therefore, according to the Art.27 of the GA, we are obliged to protect such results before their exploitation and the sensitive data (e.g. experimental details; graphs; etc.) are not presented in this deliverable D5.1.

2. Samples

This deliverable is focused on the biomarker A β 1-42. We bought the white lyophilized powder of A β 1-42 from Sigma Aldrich (code AG912) and we tested the DSS technology first with pure protein samples prepared in the lab by diluting the protein in distilled water. The powder was resuspended in 1% ammonium hydroxide solution (NH₄OH) (Sigma-Aldrich 221228) at a concentration of 1 mg/ml, sonicated for 30 s and stored undiluted at -20°C, according to manufacturing procedures. We prepared 5X serial dilutions in distilled water: 100 pg/mL, 20 pg/mL, 4 pg/mL, 0.8 pg/mL, 0.16 pg/mL. We performed size and Z-potential analysis which results (not reported here for confidentiality reasons) demonstrate the negative net charge of the protein and hence the suitability to deposit the protein by DSS on amine glass slides with a net positive charge on the surface. Among the different functionalized slides commercially available for immunoreaction protocols we used the amine surfaces provided by PolyAn (Berlin), which bind the molecules through an electrostatic adsorption (see figure below).

Amine Surfaces

for non-covalent coupling of negatively charged biochemical species
via electrostatic adsorption

Schematic view of the surface of amine glass slides from PolyAn (Berlin).

The dissociation energy for typical electrostatic bond is 130 kJ/mol. It is about a third of the strength of an average covalent bond. Other functionalized slides were tested such as the slides with epoxy surfaces to promote a covalent coupling of N-terminal biochemical species. Epoxides are cyclic ethers with a highly strained three-member ring. Epoxy rings can be easily reacted with nucleophiles e.g. amines, hydrazines, thiols, hydroxides and carboxyl groups. Compared to NHS esters or 1,4-Phenylene isothiocyanates (PDITC) the epoxy surface is more stable and has a longer shelf-life. Epoxy surfaces are stable up to temperatures of 40° C and are also more stable against humidity compared to NHS and PDITC-surfaces. The nucleophilic addition is catalysed by acid or basic conditions. Under acidic conditions, the oxygen in the ring is positively charged, which facilitates the nucleophilic attack. Under basic conditions the least substituted carbon is attacked by the applied nucleophile in a standard SN2 reaction. For activation of epoxy surfaces a pre-treatment with triethylamine was carried out for 10 minutes at room temperature. We do not report here the results obtained with epoxy slides due to poor repeatability. Further studies are needed to standardize the pre-treatment of the slides able to promote the covalent binding.

As suggested by the reviewers, we focused our attention on body fluids poorer in proteins compared to plasma, such as urine and saliva, to reduce the impact of non-specific binding. For these reasons, we tested the DSS technology in the last two months of the project with commercial urine-like and saliva-like fluids usually employed just for testing new biosensors. We bought them from Biochemizone and the screenshots below show the main components.

Major Composition: (Y/N) Y

CAS: 7447-40-7 Potassium Chloride
 CAS: 7778-77-0 Potassium Phosphate
 CAS: 7647-14-5 Sodium Chloride
 CAS: 10035-04-8 Calcium Chloride Dihydrate
 CAS: 791-18-6 Magnesium Chloride
 CAS: 9004-32-4 Carboxymethyl cellulose sodium
 CAS: 7558-79-4 Sodium Phosphate, dibasic
 CAS: 99-76-3 methyl 4-hydroxybenzoate
 CAS: 7732-18-5 Water, distilled Water, deionized Water
 Enzyme: Amylase, Lysozyme (customizable)
 Stabilizer: Y (customizable)
 Viscosity Enhancer: Mucin: Y (customizable)

Major Components: (Y/N) Y

Ammonium Chloride
 Calcium chloride dihydrate
 Magnesium Sulphate
 Potassium Chloride
 Sodium Chloride
 Sodium Phosphate, dibasic
 Sodium Citrate
 Sodium sulfate decahydrate
 Sodium phosphate monobasic monohydrate
 Optional: Urea, Creatinine hydrochloride, Sodium Sulphite: (Y/N) Y

Composition of the artificial saliva (left) and of the artificial urine (right).

3. Calibration tests

The A β 1-42 samples in distilled water (see dilutions in the previous section) were deposited by using the DSS. Afterwards the slide was incubated in a humid chamber for 2 h at 25 °C. For saturating excess protein-binding sites, the slide was covered with 2 mL of ArrayIt Blocking solution (BlockIt Blocking buffer) for 1 h at 25 °C. The blocking solution was used to dilute the antibody solutions. Then the slide was washed by placing it in a Petri dish with 10 mL of PBS 1X (Gibco 10010023) for 2 min. This washing cycle (WC) was repeated for three times. A solution of primary antibody, 2 mL of rabbit anti- β -Amyloid 1-42 (CellSignaling Technologies Rabbit D9A3A) at the dilution of 1:1600 was deposited on the slide and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The WCs were repeated. Finally, the secondary antibody solution (ThermoFisher Scientific anti-Rabbit I A32733), at the concentration of 0.5 μ g/mL, was incubated 1 h at 25 °C and the WCs were repeated. The figure below shows the schematic view of the immunoreaction protocol.

Immunoreaction scheme.

The mean fluorescence intensity of the spots (not reported here for confidentiality reasons) increased with increasing solution concentration with a LOD of 0.16 pg/mL and with a linear behaviour in the range tested from 0.16 pg/mL to 100 pg/mL. This is an important result which demonstrates the ability of DSS technology to achieve sub-picogram LOD for the A β 1-42 target in pure solutions diluted in distilled water.

Concerning the tests in body fluids we first tested the behaviour of the artificial body fluids in the DSS module to achieve accumulated spots. This behaviour was studied over ten replicates of spots on a single slide and over three different slides, by observing and recording the side view of the droplets during p-jet stimulation in the DSS module. The images (not shown here for confidentiality reasons) demonstrate how the behaviour is completely different for the different fluids tested. We prepared artificial plasma samples by mixing fetal bovine serum 5% in distilled water. We observed pin clogging effect just after about 10-15 min, while a 10% solution of FBS clogged the pin after about 1-2 min. We believe that additional research activity is required in future to study more deeply the plasma-based samples to avoid pin clogging, for example by mixing the samples with appropriate buffers. In fact, due to the limited time at disposal we decided to test other body fluids also in agreement with the suggestions from the external monitor experts.

The saliva sample exhibits a high evaporation point with the liquid standing on the surface of the slide even after successive depositions. This tends to enlarge the spot preventing the accumulation of the molecules. We tested the immunoreaction protocol on DSS spots of A β 1-42 diluted in saliva-like fluid at a concentration of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 500 pg/mL even with saliva-like diluted at 20%, 40% and 60% in distilled water. No significant signal was obtained. We believe that the saliva samples require additional studies in a future research project.

We performed a similar study with the artificial urine and the results (not yet published) demonstrate the ability to accumulate the droplets of artificial urine on spots of 200 μm diameter in average. We tested the DSS technology with a sample of secondary antibody (Ab2) Goat anti-Rabbit IgG highly cross-adsorbed with Alexa Fluor plus 647 diluted at 500 pg/mL and 0.8 pg/mL in urine-like fluid. Ten replicates of the spots on three replicated slides were produced by DSS and the fluorescence intensity of the spots with Ab2 had a signal 2 times higher than that of blank spots (only urine-like). This demonstrated clearly the ability of DSS to concentrate a low abundant sample of a labelled protein used as probe down to sub-picogram level of detection in urine-like fluid. Then, we tested the whole immunoreaction protocol on DSS spots of A β 1-42 diluted in urine-like fluid at a concentration of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 400 ng/mL. The results (not reported here for confidentiality reasons) demonstrate the ability to detect the A β 1-42 at 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in urine-like with a signal 2.4 higher than that of the blank spots (only urine-like), while the spots at 400 ng/mL and even lower concentrations need further studies due to the non-negligible contribution of the background signal produced mainly by random deviations in the manual procedure. We believe that a more careful standardization of the protocol steps would improve significantly the signal from the target spots, considering that a sub-picogram detection in urine-like samples have been obtained with the Ab2 samples mentioned above. It is important to note that in case of low abundant samples we observed a non-negligible volume of

solid-like structure growing on each spot during jetting, probably related to the precipitation of salts in urine-like fluid. This may represent a non-negligible issue in the successive steps of the immunoreaction protocol, by hindering the immobilization of the molecules on the slide surface. Further studies are needed also for mitigating this issue, for example by pre-filtering the samples from ions that may be responsible of salt precipitation.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the prototype of the DSS module has been demonstrated to be successful for detecting the biomarker A β 1-42 with a LOD of 0.8 pg/mL and a linear behaviour in the range 0.8 – 100 pg/mL in case of pure reference samples in distilled water solvent. Moreover, the comparative study performed with a commercial piezo-based biospotter (see D4.2) represents a benchmarking exercise which demonstrates the ability of DSS technology to concentrate biomolecules in tiny droplets in a reliable manner. These results open the route for developing the DSS technology also for applications in the field of microarray spotting.

The experiments on body fluids were performed in a too short period of time (a couple of months) due to the lack of automated liquid handling from Ginolis. However, it is noteworthy that significant results have been achieved which demonstrate how urine-like samples can be split and stack by the DSS technology. A sub-picogram level of detection has been achieved by using a fluorescent probe protein Ab2 and promising results have been obtained in case of a complete immunoreaction protocol. The results are currently under consideration for publication in a scientific peer reviewed paper. Anyway, the results achieved in urine samples are promising and further studies will be performed in a future project to achieve a calibration curve of the super-sensor especially in urine samples which provided better results. The DSS prototype will need the integration with an automated system for liquid handling in the reaction steps and alternative protocol procedures will be tested, such as labelled primary antibody and sandwich-like configurations with glass slides functionalized with a primary antibody. Moreover, even binding mechanisms stronger than the electrostatic one used here will be studied in a future project to reduce the detrimental impact of non-specific signals.